

COURTESY ATTITUDE TO MOTIVATION AND THE IMPLICATIONS ON THE PERFORMANCE OF CIVIL SERVANTS IN BANYUASIN REGENCY

HENDRA HADIWIJAYA¹, SULASTRI^{2*}, AGUSTINA HANAFTI³ and MARLINA
WIDIYANTI⁴

¹Doctoral Program Management Students, Universitas Sriwijaya, Palembang, Indonesia.

^{2,3,4}Faculty of Economic, Universitas Sriwijaya Palembang, Indonesia.

Email: hendra_hadi@palcomtech.ac.id¹, sulastri2310@gmail.com^{2*}, agustinahanafi@fe.unsri.ac.id³,
marlinawidiyanti68@yahoo.co.id⁴

Abstract

The study is to prove the effect of courtesy on motivation and the implications for the performance of civil servants in Banyuasin Regency. The sample of this research consisted of Civil Servants with structural positions of echelon IV as many as 373 people in the local government of Banyuasin Regency. Technical analysis of data using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) with a Variance or Component Based (VB-SEM) approach with Partial Least Squares (PLS) technique. The results showed that the Courtesy Attitude Variable had a positive effect on Employee Performance and Courtesy Attitude had a positive effect on Motivation. This study also proved that motivation had a positive effect on employee performance. It concludes that the Motivation Variable as an intervention variable between courtesy and employee performance. This research has implications for policies for performance appraisal that are based on courtesy and motivation.

Keywords: Courtesy, Motivation, Employee Performance

INTRODUCTION

Clean government prioritizes the performance improvement to realize good governance. Human Resources (HR) plays a major role in the success of an organization. Many organizations realize that the human element can provide a competitive advantage such as setting goals, strategies, innovation, and achieving organizational goals. Therefore, human resource is one of the most vital elements for an organization (Anwar & Abdullah, 2021; Supratman et al., 2021). Furthermore, organizations are required to have new ways to maintain and improve employee performance so that they can make a maximum contribution to the organization, (Al-zagheer et al., 2022; Bazrkar & Moshiripour, 2021; Munir et al., 2021). Basically, some organizations/agencies expect good performance from each of their employees in order to contribute to organizational development. The emphasis on performance-based management of the State Civil Apparatus has emerged since the birth of Law no. 5 of 2014 concerning State Civil Apparatus (UU ASN). Performance appraisal of Civil Servants aims to ensure the objectivity of coaching based on the achievement system and career system. Good performance civil servants will get appreciation or rewards and the promotions. On the other hand, civil servants with poor performance will have the potential to be subject to sanctions. The leaders have an important role in the success of organization. The organizations will be successful if they have leaders with good vision for the future to respond to changes that occur

in the organizational environment. The leaders will be successful if they are supported by subordinates with good performance and vice versa, subordinates will have good performance if they have the leaders who are able to motivate, build effective relationships and are able to plan and implement changes in the organization.

Organizational leaders always try to develop human resources to obtain good quality performance, so they can achieve the planned organizational goals (Roper & Higgins, 2020). Performance is the result of work in quality and quantity achieved by an employee in carrying out the task in accordance with the responsibilities given, (Pradhan & Jena, 2017). Performance becomes a real behavior displayed as an achievement produced by an employee in accordance with the authority and responsibility with the tasks assigned to him. Mathis & Jackson, (2018) argue that performance is defined as results-based information that focuses on employee achievement. In the type of work, the (quantitative) measures are obvious; the results-based information approach may be more successful. Performance indicators include: number of results, quality of results, effectiveness, efficiency/timeliness of results (Smith et al., 2018).

Performance achievement can be explained by goal setting theory. The implementation of goal setting proposed Locke, (1968) the goal setting process must involve leaders and subordinates simultaneously in determining or setting the goals or work objectives carried out. In the implementation of goal setting as the main foundation of the theory, namely: (1) specific goals, (2) relevant goals, (3) challenges or difficulty levels of goals, (4) goal commitment, (5) goal participation, and (6) feedback.

Goal setting theory can be an effective method in motivating members of an organization, (Locke & Latham, 2006), (McShane & Von Glinow, 2010), (Greenberg, 2011), (Dubrin, 2012). The concept of motivation is to describe the direction, magnitude (level of effort), and duration (or persistence) of behavior. To deepen the motivation related to attitudes and behavior using the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA), because attitudes and behavior are from the feelings felt by a person to accept or reject attitudes and behaviors measured as good or bad, agree or reject. This theory emphasizes the role of a person "intention" in determining the behavior that will occur (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975 & 1980). Someone who thinks about goals, then they are required to be able to consider the meaning in achieving them, especially when the goal is hard, (Locke et al., 1981; Pinder, 2008). The concept of Goal setting and Theory of Reasoned Action cannot be separated to increase work motivation and increase performance, (Fishbein & Ajzen, 1975, 1980; Locke, 1968; Quick, 1979).

Empirical studies showed that the level of motivation in an employee affects the activities that are carried out by the employee to meet the performance, (Hadiwijaya, 2015; Shaaban, 2018). Research conducted by Rini et al. (2021) found that management commitment can increase work motivation. This research provides that theoretical development can improve ranking and competitiveness through the strength of teamwork. The positive behavior of people in the organization, expressed in the form of a conscious and voluntary willingness to work has a positive impact not only on themselves, but also contributes to the organization more than that is formally required by the organization. Voluntary action behavior carried out by individuals

even though these actions are not part of their duties as members of the organization, but on the initiative to make the best contribution to the organization, (Asgari et al., 2019). Employees who contribute to organizational effectiveness by performing things outside of their main duties or roles are assets to the organization (Luthans, 2011). Refers to the behavior of employees who make a positive contribution to the organization, (Jafari & Majidi-Moghadam, 2013). Research conducted by Erum et al. (2020) showed that motivation was affected by positive behavior.

Shaaban (2018) showed the results that the positive behavior of people in the organization can be developed through the application of extrinsic motivation and intrinsic motivation among employees and supports the mediating role of employee engagement. In this case, courtesy can support employee involvement in building a conducive working relationship which in turn can improve performance. In contrast to the research of Suyantiningsih, Haryono, and Zami (2018) showed that behavior had a direct effect on performance without being mediated by motivation

DBased on previous studies related to the influence of attitudes on motivation and performance there were gaps. Research conducted by Adeniji et al., (2018), Sultana & Malik, (2019) results of the study showed that attitude had no effect on motivation and performance. In contrast to the research of Adisa et al., (2020), Alfandi, (2019), Asif et al., (2013), Cherian et al., (2021), Efendi, (2021), Erum et al., (2020) Günay, (2018), Hermawati & Mas, (2017), Ibrahim et al., (2020), Ismail et al., (2018), Kissi et al., (2019), Manzoor et al., (2021), Ribeiro et al., (2018), Ridwan et al., (2020), Rini et al., (2021), Rita et al., (2018), Safaa, (2018) Sani & Ekowati, (2020), Suyantiningsih et al., (2018), Vipraprastha et al., (2018), Hadiwijaya, (2017) research results showed that attitude had a positive and significant effect on motivation and performance.

The courtesy attitude of employees in the organization is necessary because it can create a good impression about the employee among their co-workers, the more employees who have a positive attitude, the better organization will be (Kinicki & Fugate, 2012). The positive attitude of employees is very important for the smooth functioning of the organization and its direct effect on performance, so the organization should not only focus on work experience but also be able to adopt an attitude-based selection procedure (Kumar et al., 2009). In the Kalender and Holmberg (2019) Courtesy is recognized as part of an accountable work and an important part of quality assurance in service. The emotional part of Courtesy consists of a little bit of charming and flattering. Courtesy is a discreet way to overcome the tension between conflicting goals, (Wadmann & Hoeyer, 2014).

RESEARCH METHODS

The research sample consisted of civil servants with structural positions of echelon IV as many as 373 people consisting of 240 people of echelon IV a and 133 people of echelon IV b in Banyuasin Regency. The method of determining the sample using the saturated sample method (census). Technical analysis of the data in this study using Structural Equation Modeling

(SEM) with a Variance or Component Based (VB-SEM) approach with Partial Least Squares (PLS) techniques.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Confirmatory Factor Analysis is used to confirm among variables the effect of courtesy on motivation and the implications for employee performance. Confirmatory factor analysis is designed to test the un-dimensionality of a theoretical construct, or often referred to as testing the validity and reliability of a theoretical construct.

Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA)

The dimensional validity test of the constructs in this study was carried out by looking at the standard factor load values of each indicator in the overall model (full model). The indicator is declared valid if the standard factor load had value greater than 0.5. The reliability test was done by looking at the Composite Reliability value in the full model. The indicator was declared good if it has a value > 0.6 . The measurement of the model to test the validity and reliability of the latent construct forming indicators was carried out by confirmatory factor analysis (CFA). On Model_1 CFA Constructs Exogenous (Courtesy Attitude) and Endogenous (Motivation, Employee Performance)

Figure 1: CFA_1 Test Exogenous and Endogenous

Based on Figure 1, the Exogenous CFA test on the Courtesy Attitude variable and the Endogenous CFA test on the Motivation and Employee performance variables had a loading factor value of < 0.5 , namely the SCPP02 indicator on the Courtesy Attitude variable, MKKP02, MKKP03 on the Motivation variable, KPEF01, KPEF02, KPKW02, KPKW03 on the Performance variable, it means that the indicator was not valid and must be removed, so that Model_2 CFA of Exogenous and Endogenous Constructs is obtained:

Figure 2: CFA- Final Exogenous and Endogenous Model Test

Based on Figure 2 Test of CFA- Final Exogenous and Endogenous Models, there was no load factor loading value < 0.5 . All indicators on exogenous constructs and endogenous constructs were valid. The results of reliability calculations using Composite Reliability from Confirmatory Factor Analysis / CFA for exogenous and endogenous variables showed that all research variables in the full model had good reliability.

Table 1: Exogenous Loading Factor and Composite Reliability Value

Variable	Construct	Loading factor ($> 0,5$)	Composite Reliability ($> 0,7$)	Description
Courtesy Attitude ξ	SCPP01	0.776	0.884	Valid & Reliable
	SCPP03	0.782		Valid & Reliable
	SCSP01	0.631		Valid & Reliable
	SCSP02	0.556		Valid & Reliable
	SCSP03	0.762		Valid & Reliable
	SCTR01	0.632		Valid & Reliable
	SCTR02	0.765		Valid & Reliable
	SCTR03	0.776		Valid & Reliable
Motivation η_1	MKKA01	0.847	0.900	Valid & Reliable
	MKKA02	0.732		Valid & Reliable
	MKKK01	0.819		Valid & Reliable
	MKKK02	0.695		Valid & Reliable
	MKKK03	0.651		Valid & Reliable
	MKKP01	0.697		Valid & Reliable
	MKK03	0.801		Valid & Reliable
Employee performance η_2	KPKK01	0.734	0.910	Valid & Reliable
	KPKK02	0.794		Valid & Reliable
	KPKK03	0.759		Valid & Reliable
	KPKL01	0.647		Valid & Reliable
	KPKL02	0.710		Valid & Reliable
	KPKN01	0.710		Valid & Reliable
	KPKN02	0.841		Valid & Reliable
	KPKW01	0.776		Valid & Reliable

Source: Processed Primary Data , 2022

Table 2: Coefficient value and t-count at 5% level

Variable	Coefficient	t-count (>1,96)	P Values	Description
Courtesy -> Motivation	0.844	34,038	0.000	Signifikan
Courtesy -> Performance	0.423	7,451	0.000	Signifikan
Motivation -> Performance	0.518	9,107	0.000	Signifikan
Courtesy -> Motivation -> Performance	0.437	7.900	0.000	Signifikan

Source: Data processing results (2022)

Based on the sub-structural model, it can be explained that Motivation (JS) wa directly affected by Courtesy Attitude. It showed that Courtesy's attitude had a positive effect on motivation of 0.844 for civil servants in Banyuasin Regency. Based on the structural model above, it can be explained that Employee performance was directly influenced by Courtesy Attitudes and motivation and the magnitude of the influence of Courtesy Attitudes on Employee Performance for Employees was 0.423, Motivation on Employee Performance was 0.518. This means that motivation had a greater influence on employee performance in civil servants in Banyuasin Regency.

DISCUSSION

Table 3: Direct and Indirect Effect

Effect	Coefficient
Courtesy → Motivation	0.844
Motivation → Performance	0.423
Courtesy → Performance	0.423
Courtesy → Motivation → Performance	0.437

Source: Data processing results, 2022

Based on Table 3, it showed that the coefficient value of the direct influence of Courtesy Attitude on Motivation was 0.844, Motivation on performance was 0.518, and the coefficient value of the direct influence of Courtesy Attitude on performance was 0.423. The coefficient of indirect influence of Courtesy Attitudes on Employee Performance with Motivation as an intervening variable was 0.437

Employees who contribute to organizational effectiveness by performing things outside their main duties or roles as the assets to the organization (Luthans, 2011). Based on the behavior of employees who make a positive contribution to the organization, (Jafari & Majidi-Moghadam, 2013). Erum et al. (2020) research showed that the relationship of effective commitment with family motivation and modesty was partially mediated while the relationship of positive behavior of people in the organization with family motivation and politeness was fully mediated by self-efficacy. In Shaaban's research (2018), the results revealed that the positive behavior of people in the organization can be developed through the application of extrinsic motivation and intrinsic motivation among employees and supports the mediating role

of employee engagement. Suyantiningsih, Haryono, and Zami (2018) showed that the positive behavior of people in the organization had a positive effect on performance. This study also showed a significant positive effect of job satisfaction on employee performance.

Based on the results of previous studies related to the influence of attitudes on motivation and performance, there were still gaps. Research conducted by Adeniji et al., (2018), Sultana & Malik, (2019) showed that attitude had no effect on motivation and performance. In contrast to the research of Adisa et al., (2020), Alfandi, (2019), Asif et al., (2013), Cherian et al., (2021), Efendi, (2021), Erum et al., (2020) Günay, (2018), Hermawati & Mas, (2017), Ibrahim et al., (2020), Ismail et al., (2018), Kissi et al., (2019), Manzoor et al., (2021), Ribeiro et al., (2018), Ridwan et al., (2020), Rini et al., (2021), Rita et al., (2018), Safaa, (2018) Sani & Ekowati, (2020), Suyantiningsih et al., (2018), Vipraprastha et al., (2018) research results showed that attitude had a positive and significant effect on motivation and performance. To improve relationships between individuals, avoid and resolve personal conflicts, reduce uncertainty, share knowledge and experiences with others, control behavior, motivate, express emotions, and provide information.

CONCLUSION

Courtesy Attitude variable had a positive and insignificant effect with t-count $7.451 > 1.96$, p-values $0.00 < 0.05$ on Employee performance. Courtesy attitude had a positive and significant effect with t-count of $34.038 > 1.96$, p-values $0.000 < 0.05$ on Motivation. Motivation variable had a positive and significant effect with t-count of $9.107 > 1.96$, p-value of $0.000 < 0.05$ on Employee performance. Motivation variable had a positive and significant effect with a t-count of $7.900 > 1.96$, p-value $0.000 < 0.05$ on Employee performance with Motivation as an intervening variable for Civil Servants in Banyuasin Regency.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This research is supported by the Ministry of Education, Culture, Research and Technology through the Doctoral Dissertation Research scheme. This research is also supported by the Faculty of Economics, Sriwijaya University and Institute of Research and Community Service (LPPM), Sriwijaya University.

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